

iREAL: Inclusive Requirements Elicitation for AI in Libraries to Support Respectful Management of Indigenous Knowledges. Literature Review

iREAL: Inclusive Requirements for AI in Libraries to Support Respectful Management of Indigenous Knowledges

Literature Review

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Executive Summary

This literature review was produced by the iREAL project team to investigate the relationship between Indigenous Knowledges, library collections, and Artificial Intelligence systems design and critique. The review is presented in five sections on the following topics: i.) the relationship between Indigenous knowledges and Western knowledges; ii.) library approaches to Indigenous knowledge systems; iii.) Indigenising the Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAM) sector; iv.) the link between colonial logics of progression and subsequent data violence; and v.) the application of principles of Indigenous self-determination and sovereignty to decision-making around AI applications in libraries. It recommends areas of intervention that can guide libraries working with AI and Indigenous knowledges in the requirements elicitation process.

All artwork produced by Reuben Raymond (Larrakia/Yindjibarndi artist), and commissioned via [Nani Creative](#): Further information is available at the [iREAL website](#).

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Note on Terminology

In this work, we adopt the words 'Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander' and 'Aboriginal' interchangeably, referring to the First Peoples of the land we now call Australia and the Torres Strait Islands. The terms 'Indigenous' and 'First Nations' are used to refer to other communities and nations outside Australia. Whenever possible, we include peoples' areas and language groups.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
1.1 Scope and methodology	7
1.2 Situating iREAL in relation to existing literature	8
1.3 Summary of themes.....	8
2. Indigenous Knowledges on the Global Scene	8
2.1 Indigenous Knowledges: relational ways of being, thinking, doing, and valuing	9
2.2 Western epistemology and ontology: a colonial logic of dehumanisation.....	10
2.3. Settler colonial Sovereignties of ownership: possession through elimination.....	10
2.4. The land we now call Australia	11
3. Indigenous Knowledges, GLAMs and the Settler Colonial Logic of Possessiveness.....	13
3.1. Colonialism, data violence, and the creation of Indigenous deficiency.....	13
3.2. Recordkeeping, data, archive, and settler colonial sovereignty.....	13
3.4. GLAMs as sites of Indigenous misrepresentation, appropriation, and elimination	14
4. Indigenizing AI of/in GLAMs: Creating Digitised Spaces of Indigenous Sovereignty and Self-determination	16
4.1. Indigenous (re)presenting in GLAMs: a note on decolonisation and Indigenisation.....	16
4.2. Decolonising and Indigenising the archive: centring Indigenous Knowledges and community-oriented approaches	16
4.3. Indigenous relational knowledges as decolonising and Indigenising research projects	17
4.4. Indigenous sovereignty and self-determination in GLAMs: moving beyond metaphorical decolonisation and symbolic recognition	18
4.5. The United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples and other protocols and consequent standards	19
5. Indigenising AI for Indigenous Archives and Knowledge Management in GLAMs.....	21
5.1. Indigenous data sovereignty.....	21
5.2. FAIR and CARE for open data	22
5.3. Focus on frameworks	22
5.4. Challenges and opportunities of AI for Indigenous Peoples and Knowledges	23
5.5. Learning from and getting inspired by Indigenous use of AI technologies	23
6. Recommendations.....	26
References	27

1. Introduction

The project *iREAL: Inclusive Requirements Elicitation for AI in Libraries to Support Respectful Management of Indigenous Knowledges* is a collaboration between the University of Glasgow, the Jumbunna Institute for Indigenous Education and Research (Jumbunna Research) at the University of Technology Sydney (UTS), King's College London and the Digital Preservation Coalition. The project aims to:

- Centre Indigenous rights and perspectives in the AI requirements elicitation process in libraries
- Ground the Right to Know and the Right to Reply in discussions of library AI applications with respect to knowledges from Indigenous communities, specifically Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities in Australia
- Produce guidance and a framework for the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) sector to use from the moment organisations think of adopting or designing AI systems and models
- Critique, problematise, and scrutinise approaches to AI in theory and practice in libraries
- Centre principles of Indigenous sovereignty and self-determination in decision making around AI applications in libraries

These objectives emerged in response to the challenge of adopting Responsible AI principles, understood broadly as the responsible development and governance of AI systems (Vallor 2023) in the library sector. UK and Australian institutions hold collections from many Indigenous communities, each with its own knowledge structures and perspectives on data governance. Indigenous researchers have proposed guidelines for Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Governance (Maiam nayri Wingara 2018) and Indigenous-centred AI design (Lewis 2020). In libraries, Thomas Padilla has proposed adopting the concept of *responsible operations* as a guiding principle for developing “individual, organizational, and community capacities to support responsible use of data science, machine learning and AI” (Padilla 2019, 7). However, there is still a gap in our understanding of how these interact with Responsible AI principles as they might be applied to Indigenous knowledges held in libraries.

Requirements elicitation has been widely used in business analysis to uncover, identify and prioritise requirements for a business change or solution. A requirement is “a service, function or feature that a user needs. Requirements can be functions, constraints, business rules or other elements that must be present to meet the need of the intended users” (Agile Business, 2014). In IT and business management, requirements elicitation refers explicitly to the elicitation process – from relevant stakeholders or user groups – of general (e.g. legal), technical (e.g. internet connection, minimal computing)(Risam and Gil, 2022), functional (e.g. data processing) and non-functional (e.g. accessibility) requirements relating to the creation of a new system or process and the associated activities to support such elicitation. While the framework of such activities is defined, their implementation and combination vary based on context. Business Analysis theory and practices have moved away from a concept of “passive” requirements gathering exercise to give importance to requirements elicitation as a crucial stage of business analysis requiring an inclusive “proactive approach” underpinned by communication and interaction with key stakeholders and informed by a set of analysis techniques. The recognition that tacit knowledge and assumptions are often more important to define requirements than explicit declarations require equipping analysts with methods to understand and enable stakeholders to articulate, for example, “cultural and languages differences” or other individual and corporate elements of tacit knowledge (Paul and Cadle, 2020, 264-267). The space around the definition of requirements (in particular, the so-called general and

non-functional typology) and this attention to contexts of knowledge is where requirements elicitation approaches intersect with the sort of intervention the iREAL project aims to propose.

A key reference point for this project is the King's Digital Lab (KDL) Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC) (King's Digital Lab, 2019), which positions the process of requirements elicitation as a crucial stage of its "Requirements Assessment" phase. Building on IT industry standards,¹ KDL adapted its SDLC to the research context within which the KDL team operates and created a toolkit for documentation and processes to support software development in all their collaborative projects. It has been applied also when working in partnership within the context of libraries and other GLAM organisations. While this Literature Review adopts a broader lens, focusing on the application of Indigenous ethical principles to AI development in libraries, our intention is that it will inform subsequent work on developing guidance for GLAM organisations.

In response to the above objectives, this Literature Review highlights current practices, issues, and opportunities to develop a deeper understanding of the relationship between the ethics relating to Indigenous knowledges, and the application of Responsible AI principles in the library sector. It outlines the scope and methodology of the iREAL project, synthesises several interrelated bodies of relevant literature, and develops a set of recommendations that will provide a baseline for determining areas for further development.

1.1 Scope and methodology

As a time-limited, desk research-based project, this Literature Review is intended to work alongside the iREAL Final Project Report to inform the theoretical and methodological framework of our proposed interventions into requirements elicitation for AI in libraries. The review draws on three main streams of research:

- Existing literature comprising academic works and other published material, online sources (including websites and published videos), non-academic books and media articles considered primary sources
- Community initiatives and projects
- Resources presented and shared at the first project workshop, held in Ngunnawal Country (Canberra) in May 2024.

The parameters for this Literature Review were set at the beginning of the project collaboratively by the project team. Within these boundaries, a priority was to highlight current work and local initiatives by First Nations peoples. This work integrates a broad international perspective with the Australian context, keeping the global and the local always in balance. While the review predominantly discusses First Nations voices and viewpoints, it also incorporates insights from non-Indigenous authors, especially in the study of AI technologies. Furthermore, while the iREAL project focuses primarily on the library context, the Literature Review considers the broader GLAM sector to provide a deeper understanding of the historical use and exploitation of Indigenous knowledges, as well as the various areas where AI utilises datasets and other contextual information.

Due to time constraints and the large breadth of the thematic areas to be covered, this review focuses on undertakings and initiatives developed by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples that have been published in academic literature. Nevertheless, this parameter served as a valuable starting point for developing recommendations for community-based projects in specific locations, which could be better documented in the future to establish a baseline of existing initiatives. Another

¹ Particularly the Agile DSDM framework (Agile Business Consortium. *The DSDM Agile Project Framework Handbook*. DSDM Consortium, 2014, <https://www.agilebusiness.org/dsdm-project-framework.html>.)

limitation of this work is that it excludes works that could have been published in languages other than English.

1.2 Situating iREAL in relation to existing literature

In line with the iREAL project methodology, which draws inspiration from Indigenous authors, worldviews, and methodological approaches, this literature review is grounded upon the *Right to Know* and the *Right to Reply* of Indigenous peoples regarding how their information is disseminated (Indigenous Archives Collective 2021; O’Neal 2015). Both rights require an active dialogue with and participation of Indigenous communities. We therefore draw closely upon thinking from Indigenous authors. Further details of the overall project methodology can be found in the final iREAL report.

The themes of this Literature Review emerged from consideration of the foundational works and existing knowledge in the field of AI for the cultural sector, its potential, challenges and limitations. Some key areas that emerged strongly were:

- The potential for libraries to integrate AI into their daily practices and to serve as community leaders, in contrast to large corporations that primarily profit financially from AI use (Cordell 2020)
- The need for interdisciplinary and diverse teams to tackle future AI challenges (Cordell 2020)
- The biases in AI algorithms (Australian Human Rights Commission 2020; European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights 2022; Kordzadeh and Ghasemaghaei 2021; Noble 2018)
- The exploitation that AI technologies bring to people, privacy and land, whilst perpetuating social inequalities (Bradley 2022; Crawford 2022; Hajri 2023)
- The constant rise of AI regulation in Europe and other sectors and states (UNESCO 2021)

However, this body of work focuses on the application of AI and machine learning for managing Indigenous Knowledge within libraries and the broader information sector, including:

- Indigenous rights of sovereignty and self-determination
- Indigenous research methodologies and methods in the context of AI in libraries
- Land-based and community-based research methodologies for Indigenous archival frameworks and stewardship
- Local protocols and principles for Indigenous archival sovereignty and knowledge management
- Local and global guidelines for Indigenous self-determination and data sovereignty
- Current models for the management of Indigenous knowledges in collecting institutions (physical and digital)
- Indigenous Interventions in AI value chains and AI ethics
- Guidelines for Indigenous-centred AI systems

1.3 Summary of themes

This Literature Review comprises five main sections. The first outlines the relationship between Indigenous knowledges and Western knowledges in the context of colonial and settler projects worldwide. The second establishes the context for this project by critiquing and problematising library and information systems approaches when dealing with Indigenous knowledge systems. The third discusses the literature that encourages the need for Indigenising the GLAM sector. The fourth reflects on colonial logics of possession and consequent data violence. The fifth section focuses on literature dedicated to Indigenous sovereignty and self-determination in decision-making around AI applications in libraries. The final section synthesises the findings from this Literature Review to propose approaches for this project and outline recommendations for future work, guiding interventions in the requirements elicitation process.

2. Indigenous Knowledges on the Global Scene

Exercising Indigenous Data Governance enables Indigenous peoples, our representative and governing bodies to accurately reflect our stories. It provides the necessary tools to identify what works, what does not and why. Effective Indigenous Data Governance empowers our peoples to make the best decisions to support our communities and First Nations in the ways that meet our development needs and aspirations.

Maiaam nayri Wingara Indigenous Data Sovereignty Collective and the Australian Indigenous Governance Institute, "Indigenous Data Sovereignty Communique" (2018).

2.1 Indigenous Knowledges: relational ways of being, thinking, doing, and valuing

Recent data indicate that there are approximately 476 million Indigenous peoples around the world spread across over 5,000 distinct communities with cultures that are as different as the 4000 different languages they speak (UNESCO 2021). Indigenous knowledges *can*² be conceived as holistic, interrelated, and polycephalic systems of epistemology (ways of knowing), ontology (ways of being), and methodology (ways of doing) that touch upon a wide array of interdependent domains such as everyday life, law, ethics, decision-making, social and emotional wellbeing, philosophy, culture and spirituality, ecology, biology, medicine, cosmology, astrology, and geography (Dudgeon et al. 2023; Dudgeon, Gibson, and Bray 2021; Kincheloe and Steinberg 2008). Indigenous knowledges are neither timeless nor static. Rather, they have evolved and adapted to different socio-political and environmental realities faced by Indigenous peoples around the world (Bredlid and Krøvel 2020; Moore and Nestova 2020). While being varied and different in many ways, reflecting the diversity and the complexity of Indigenous peoples, histories, cultures, and worldviews globally, Indigenous knowledges share common worldviews and aspects. Indeed, these knowledges are place-based, experiential, and collectively mediated through embodied performances such as stories, ceremonies, and rituals, as well as various cultural expressions and lived experiences (Adams-Campbell, Falzetti, and Rivard 2014; Dudgeon, Gibson, and Bray 2021; Gareau and Swain 2024).

Indigenous knowledges are grounded in and expressed by the Land or Country³, which is regarded as alive and sapient, encompassing a myriad of sentient life forms that can be human or other/more-than-human (including animals, plants, waters, and spirits), entangled together within physical and spiritual relationships of co-existence, reciprocity, and kinship (Durie 2005; Chilisa 2019; Dudgeon, Gibson, and Bray 2021; Gareau and Swain 2024; Kwaymullina 2008). Thus, several Indigenous researchers argue that relationality comprises a common denominator throughout different Indigenous knowledges (Dudgeon et al. 2023; Wilson 2008). Relationality centres a worldview that stresses the importance of sustaining harmonious relationships between people and the planet or Land (Dudgeon et al. 2023). Indeed, Indigenous relational worldviews provide the ontological and epistemological understandings of Indigenous peoples' physical, spiritual/ metaphysical, and intersubjective relatedness and kinship with Land, and define the ethical and axiological aspects of their stewardship responsibilities (Dudgeon et al. 2023; Gareau and Swain 2024; Kovach 2021; Moreton-Robinson 2004, 2015; Willson 2008). Throughout the difference and distinctiveness of Indigenous knowledge systems, relationality is positioned at their crux. Relationality is a multidimensional and fluid matrix of comprehension and interpretation through which Indigenous peoples make sense of themselves and their place within the holistic realms of life that constitute their natural, socio-political, and cultural environments. Relationality is also crucial in the ways in which knowledge has been passed down orally for thousands of years, personally and collectively:

² The use and the emphasis on the modal verb "can" is intentional and expresses the need to not confine Indigenous knowledges within western terminologies that define different areas of knowledge.

³ Some Indigenous peoples use the term Land while others use the term Country. The capitalisation of these terms asserts their importance, sentience, sapience, and agency. See Redvers et al. (2022).

this dynamism means that Indigenous perspectives might lose their relevance when they are extracted and relocated to other realms (Drummond 2020).

2.2 Western epistemology and ontology: a colonial logic of dehumanisation

Indigenous peoples have seen their lifeways and knowledges disrupted by colonial projects engrained in and fuelled by ideals of Liberalism, private property, and the individual pursuit of economic gain. Indeed, the notions of rationalism, scientific positivism and free market capitalism borne out of the so-called Enlightenment, and which have dominated Western European thought and political philosophy since the eighteenth century, generated an anthropocentric, logocentric, and empiricist epistemology and ontology that imposed a universal truth. This supposed universal truth defined for centuries the validity of history, civilisation, and knowledge as associated with Western aspects of industrialisation, progress, literacy, discovery, and scientific objectivism (Little Bear 2000; Moreton-Robinson 2017; Gareau and Swain 2024; Kovach 2021). Under this light, Indigenous peoples were placed outside Western modernity and civilisation criteria. Their histories were deemed prehistorical and mythical. Their relational and holistic knowledge were considered metaphysical, relativistic, and superstitious, thus lacking objective scientific methods of validation (Little Bear 2000; Moreton-Robinson 2017; Smith 2021; Vizenor 2008). Western epistemology and ontology were instrumental in giving form and meaning to the Western ideas of *Otherness*, creating a racialised logic by which Indigenous peoples were dehumanised and objectified (Smith 2021, 35). This dehumanisation constituted a cornerstone of European imperialist thinking and served to justify the colonial enterprise and its capitalist and extractive underpinnings. This racialised logic, addressed to Indigenous peoples and other segments of society, provided an epistemological and ontological justification for the longstanding violent practices and policies that targeted Indigenous peoples and their lifeways. Colonial and settler domination across the world was not a single event but rather an ongoing, systematic process (Liboiron 2021).

2.3. Settler colonial sovereignties of ownership: possession through elimination

As a distinct form of colonialism, settler colonialism's particularity lies in its primary nature and purpose, which is oriented towards the access and control of Indigenous lands and peoples (Tuck and Yang 2012; Wolfe 1999; Wolfe 2006). As such, it posed and continues to pose a threat to Indigenous knowledges and peoples' relational sovereignties with their lands based on reciprocity and stewardship (Andersen 2003; Coulthard 2014; Coulthard and Simpson 2016; Goeman 2013; Moreton-Robinson 2004; Smith 2021). The understanding of Indigenous sovereignty and its significance varies notably among settler states, communities, and individuals. According to Eualeyai/Gamillaroi scholar Larissa Behrendt sovereignty spans a range of claims that can be organised into three main categories: equality rights (the right to non-discrimination and equal access to services, infrastructure, and opportunities); Indigenous rights (rights to culture, heritage, language, and native title); and empowerment rights (the ability to make decisions and have control over those decisions that affect Indigenous lives) (Behrendt 2013, 164). Numerous authors have highlighted how Indigenous sovereignty is distinct from state sovereignty (Jonas 2002; The Uluru Dialogue 2017), with the former needing to be understood in the context of colonisation, due to it constituting an Aboriginal method of governance since time immemorial (Reynolds 2006, quoting a Yawuru Aboriginal Elder). Crucially for this project, in recent decades there has been a growth of Indigenous movements that have been claiming that sovereignty over data and personal information is a crucially important mechanism for supporting the realisation of Indigenous aspirations, self-determination, and innovation. In practice, as Stephanie Russo Carroll (Ahtna-Native Village of Kluti-Kaah), Tahu Kukutai and Maggie Walter (Palawa) write, "Indigenous Data Sovereignty means that Indigenous peoples need to be the decision-makers around how data about them are used" (2021, 691).

Based on the Western ideology of property and ownership, settler colonialism presents a contrasting and rival worldview to that held by many Indigenous peoples in large part because it defines the state and society's relationship to land as purely commodified. This worldview is an integral part of the settler colonial imperial mindset that established and justified the superiority of Western lifeways, knowledge, and governance structures, reflected in political narratives of conquest such as the Doctrine of Discovery, Terra Nullius, and Manifest Destiny (Gareau and Swain 2024, 2; Smith 2021, 67-68). According to this imperial mindset, Indigenous peoples were discovered, dehumanised, objectified, dispossessed, eliminated, and/ or saved through the introduction and imposition of Western knowledge systems and notions of civilisation, which had significant spiritual, intellectual, social, and economic impacts (Hokowhitu 2009; Smith 2021). Deployed through various political, legal, economic, and educational institutions, the discourse of possessiveness provides a justification for settler possession of Indigenous lands, cultures, and thoughts while simultaneously legitimising the myriad violent policies and practices that targeted Indigenous peoples and knowledges based on their supposed backwardness and primitivism (Gareau and Swain 2024; Moreton-Robinson 2015; TallBear 2019). This racialised logic of whiteness inaugurated a discourse of possessiveness and ownership that is still at the heart of settler colonial states in their endeavour to replace Indigenous peoples on their lands (Moreton-Robinson 2015).

As such, the settler-colonial discourse of possessiveness and ownership is geared towards the establishment and reinforcement of white patriarchal orders that aim to normalise and naturalise their existence and sovereignty. Indeed, this discourse operated and still operates through various policies and practices of elimination and appropriation of Indigenous peoples and knowledges adapted to specific historical and political circumstances (Moreton Robinson 2015; TallBear 2019; Tuck and Yang 2012; Wolfe 2006). This started with practices and strategies of genocide, removal, and biocultural assimilation that were justified and clothed within pseudo-humanitarian discourses in academic and popular narratives. These narratives commonly implied saving Indigenous peoples from a fatal extinction of their lifeways, cultures, and knowledges (Foley 2000; Wolfe 1999; Vizenor 2009; Smith 2021).

The global rise of Indigenous activism and sovereignty movements since the 1970s has caused a shift in the settler colonial discourse of possessiveness and ownership, with neoliberal multicultural discourses often disguising policies of assimilation and genocide. As many scholars note, there has been an increase in a politics of recognition and accommodation, which aim to encase Indigenous political horizons and sovereignty within the constraint of the settler state and notions of legal ownership (Allen 2002; Byrd 2011; Coulthard 2014; Povinelli 2002; Simpson 2014; Tuck and Yang 2012). Tuck and Yang (2012) for example use the term "settler moves to innocence" to describe the "strategies or positionings that attempt to relieve the settler of feelings of guilt or responsibility without giving up land or power or privilege, without having to change much at all" (Tuck and Yang 2012, 10). For them, such moves to innocence obscure the ongoing oppression of Indigenous peoples under the discourse of multiculturalism. This results in attempts at tackling social inequities without focusing on structural racism and the victimisation of Indigenous peoples, as well as the endorsement of wealth distribution without due acknowledgement of the ongoing occupation of Indigenous lands as the source of this wealth (2012, 3-22).

2.4. The land we now call Australia

The British settlement of Australia, precipitated by the arrival of the naval officer Captain James Cook in 1770, is a relatively recent event compared to the more than 65,000 years that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples have inhabited and stewarded the land (Clarkson et al. 2017). British colonisation had a profound impact on the lives and sovereignty of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. Land was claimed under the concept of *Terra Nullius*, while discriminatory and racist policies throughout the nineteenth and twentieth centuries targeted Aboriginal identity,

language, and culture. These histories have deeply influenced Australia's national consciousness. In the 1968 Boyer Lectures, anthropologist W.E.H. Stanner described this phenomenon as the Great Australian Silence, calling it "A cult of forgetfulness practised on a national scale" (Stanner 1968). This shift in awareness has reshaped Australian historiography, opening space for new narratives by both Aboriginal and non-Indigenous historians (Clark 2024). These emerging perspectives have paralleled Aboriginal-led political movements for rights and resistance (Maynard 2007). Nonetheless, the enduring effects of these past policies are evident in the significant disparities in health, social standing, and opportunity between Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians (Australian Government 2020) and gaps that remain "unacceptably wide" (Calma 2007). Like in other settler colonial states, Australia's pursuit of truth-telling is a complex, ongoing journey that is necessary to understanding and addressing the structural inequalities that still affect Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples.

In summary, Indigenous knowledges are grounded in traditions, languages, and practices, covering diverse areas such as medicine, agriculture, astronomy, and storytelling. The analysis of the literature remarks on the differences and similarities between Indigenous communities and worldviews by asserting the importance of relationality with people, knowledge, and Country. The centrality of doctrines of dehumanisation, possession, and elimination of Indigenous people across the world to colonialism is important to context to the development of AI processes of data ownership and control. Indigenous peoples have historically been deliberately excluded from decision-making regarding their lands and prevented from practicing systems of sovereignty that had been in place since time immemorial. The histories of the unceded Countries of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples in the land we now call Australia have followed similar paths. As we shall see in the next sections, settler and colonial logics of possessiveness and whiteness have also greatly influenced the ways in which knowledge has been shared and passed through generations of Indigenous peoples, as well as collected and controlled by state authorities.

3. Indigenous Knowledges, GLAMs and the Settler Colonial Logic of Possessiveness

The artificial intelligence (AI) industry-academic complex does not have an ethics problem. It does, however, have an epistemology problem.

J.E Lewis, H. Whaanga, and C. Yolgörmez, “Abundant Intelligences: Placing AI within Indigenous Knowledge Frameworks” (2024).

3.1. Colonialism, data violence, and the creation of Indigenous deficiency

The violence operated through colonial extraction and commodification of Indigenous knowledges as well as practices of non-consensual record keeping by colonial states is visible through the datasets that are held in institutions and organisations (Carroll, Duarte, and Liboiron 2024). Data collected on and about Indigenous peoples by colonial authorities and agencies enabled practices of control, erasure, and genocide against Indigenous peoples through, for example, military reports, national censuses, and educational tests (Andersen 2008; Pearce and Williams 2013). For instance, the American Indian boarding schools in the United States of America, the Indian residential school system in Canada, and the Australian child removal policies (Stolen Generations) are all outcomes of data-driven anthropological narratives that justify the brutal biocultural assimilation of Indigenous peoples. They all had in common the pseudo-humanitarian endeavour of saving Indigenous people from extinction.

Indigenous scholars have noted how settler colonial control of data is still at the heart of Indigenous peoples' ongoing marginalisation and oppression. This is reflected in governmental reports and policies across the domains of health and wellbeing, law, and education that create narratives of deficiency, blaming Indigenous peoples for their hardships and ignoring structural problems of racism, marginalisation, and colonial traumas (Martin-Hill 2008; Nakata 2010; Paradies 2016). For instance, Eurocentric discussions around health and wellbeing in Indigenous contexts approach Indigenous hardships through a narrow prism of psychology that leads to the victimisation of Indigenous peoples and obscures the colonial and settler structures and policies that continue to produce these oppressive conditions. Palawa scholar Maggie Walter defines this as the “Indigenous data paradox”:

There is an enormous body of data about Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people but almost no data for or by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people. The mismatch maps across five categories of data failure, which I have labelled BADDR: Blaming, Aggregate, Decontextualised, Deficit and Restricted (2018, 1).

Several scholars have warned about a new era of colonialism that relies on Indigenous digital data. For example, scholar and tech expert Karaitiana Taiuru (Ngāi Tahu, Ngāti Kahungunu, Ngāti Toa) refers to data misuse as “Indigenous Digital Colonialism” (Taiuru 2015).

3.2. Recordkeeping, data, archive, and settler colonial sovereignty

The discourse of possessiveness and ownership is also operationalised through settler states' collection and control of data produced by and/or about Indigenous peoples found in governmental and private GLAM institutions in the form of archival material. Indeed, data collection, recordkeeping, and archival storage have been instrumental in establishing and legitimising colonial and settler colonial sovereignty and white supremacy (Adams-Campbell, Falzetti, and Rivard 2014; Booker 2021; Christen and Anderson 2019a; Luker 2017; McKemmish 2017; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; McKemmish, Faulkhead, and Russell 2011; McKemmish, Upward,

and Reed 2010; O'Neal 2015; Russell 2007; Stoler 2002). Indeed, from the seventeenth century, colonial agencies began documenting “artefacts” reflective of Indigenous knowledge, social systems, and technologies through a lens of “discovery,” resulting in their commodification and categorisation in Western cultural archives and museums (Smith 2021, 59, 70). Today, galleries, libraries, archives, and museums in settler states and previous imperial metropolises hold vast collections of Indigenous records, cultural artefacts, and Ancestral Remains that were “collected” through centuries of colonial extraction, becoming objects for research, teaching and instruction, tourism, and industrial commodification and simulations (MacNeil 2018; McKemmish et al. 2019; Wallace 2021). Reflecting the dispossession of Indigenous peoples and the fragmentation of Indigenous knowledges and cultural artefacts, GLAM institutions are an essential cog within the colonial and settler colonial enterprise (Booker 2021; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; Regal 2022; Thorpe 2021).

Colonial collecting and recordkeeping still play a role in establishing and maintaining conditions of resource extraction, cultural theft, appropriation, and misrepresentation of Indigenous peoples. As many authors assert, collecting institutions have never been neutral: they were conceptualised and created as active participants of colonial and settler state projects worldwide. Information, data, stories, objects, bodies and representations of Indigenous peoples have been collected and stored in different formats in collecting institutions across the world. As discussed in the next sections, several studies have explored the legacies of historical collecting that have shaped the current GLAM sector, with libraries being key sites where these surface.

3.4. GLAMs as sites of Indigenous misrepresentation, appropriation, and elimination

In addition to their extractive legacies, the colonial undersides of GLAM institutions are still present in the ways in which the curatorial methods and archival frameworks are used to approach Indigenous knowledge. These are embedded within Eurocentric knowledge systems and reflect the values and worldviews of colonial and settler colonial states (Anderson and Christen 2019a; Giaconia, Mahar, and Collins 2024; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019). This includes the separation of materials from their cultural contexts in ways that replicate the discourse of Indigenous extinction, the misrepresentation of Indigenous peoples and the misinterpretation of Indigenous knowledges and cultures in collection documentation and description. The settler colonial discourse of possessiveness and ownership is also reflected in settler states’ intellectual property regimes, which result in the commodification of data and knowledge extracted from Indigenous peoples. This extraction is replicated in the use of intellectual property laws and attribution and citation methods that privilege the researcher’s authority and voice and obscures the Indigenous contexts from which the knowledge or the material is derived (Anderson and Christen 2019a; Anderson and Christen 2019b; Giaconia, Mahar, and Collins 2024; Janke 1998; McKemmish, Faulkhead, and Russell 2011). Related to these issues is the practice of digitising Indigenous knowledge and material due to increasing calls for open data and open access. Despite being a key requirement for preservation and community access, when undertaken in silos and away from communities’ contexts and needs, these operations create dangers for Indigenous peoples and cultures. Indeed, as a number of scholars have stressed, the GLAM sector routinely fails to acknowledge the often-violent historical backdrop to the collection of this data and does not adequately respect and follow Indigenous laws and protocols, which limit access to sacred and protected forms of knowledge (Anderson and Christen 2019a; Carroll, Duarte, and Liboiron 2024; Giaconia, Mahar, and Collins 2024; Leonard et al. 2023; Wallace 2021).

In summary, colonial and settler colonial states’ control of data on or by Indigenous peoples is pivotal in its discourse of possessiveness and ownership that endeavours to legitimise the setter

states' control of sovereignty over Indigenous lands. In this way, GLAM institutions reflect a colonial perspective that often ignores Indigenous protocols for access and ownership, as well as recognition of Indigenous Cultural Intellectual Property (ICIP) rights. Datasets utilised by AI technologies today were created for and by this broad picture of possessiveness and ownership. At present, the availability of these datasets is dependent upon the institutions that legally own them. As we will discuss, there are increasing concerns with the current approaches as repeated in AI projects and models, especially when the data sources include data of which Indigenous communities are not aware. By providing representations of Indigenous knowledges in the form of machine-readable data, libraries indirectly assist AI technologies to perpetuate a cycle of dispossession and hinder Indigenous peoples' sovereignty and self-determination.

4. Indigenizing AI of/in GLAMs: Creating Digitised Spaces of Indigenous Sovereignty and Self-determination

Decolonization, once viewed as the formal process of handing over the instruments of government, is now recognized as a long-term process involving the bureaucratic, cultural, linguistic and psychological divesting of colonial power.

Linda Tuhiwai Smith, *Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples* (2021).

4.1. Indigenous (re)presentation in GLAMs: a note on decolonisation and Indigenisation

The decolonising and Indigenising work of/in the GLAM sector presents two different yet interdependent and complementary areas of research and practice. There is considerable debate over what decolonisation means for and in relation to GLAM institutions, as well as what it entails in theory and what it demands in practice. For Gibling, Ramos and Grout, “in the abstract, decolonising the museum concerns the proactive identification, interrogation, deconstruction and replacement of hierarchies of power that replication colonial structures” (2019, 472). Vergès articulates a more radical vision of decolonisation, defining it as a “programme of complete disorder” that concentrates on revealing the intrinsic violence of racial capitalism, exploring what it means to live amidst “the ruins” of this system, and imagining “a post-capitalist, post-racist, post-patriarchal future” (Vergès 2024, 152-153). While sharing some common concerns with theories and practices of decolonisation, Indigenisation is arguably more pointed in its focus and concrete in its objectives, which centre on increasing the sovereignty of Indigenous peoples, communities and lands. Within the context of GLAM institutions, this can manifest in endowing Indigenous stakeholders with greater agency and self-determination in the work of returning objects and records, defining and carrying out research, undertaking practices of care and custodianship, and digitising archives and other materials containing Indigenous knowledges. The Indigenisation of mainstream GLAM organisations depends on effective and reciprocal collaborations between an institution and Indigenous communities and between Indigenous and non-Indigenous scholars and practitioners (Anderson and Christen 2019b; Booker 2021; Carbajal and Caswell 2021; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; O’Neal 2019; Punzalan and Marsh 2022; Thorpe 2019a; Thorpe and Galassi 2014; Thorpe, Galassi, and Franks 2016; Thorpe 2024; Wallace 2021). In sum, effective and lasting change within GLAMs is incumbent on a constant intertwinement of these two agendas within the specificity of local Indigenous contexts, knowledges, histories, interests, and stewardship protocols.

4.2. Decolonising and Indigenising the archive: centring Indigenous Knowledges and community-oriented approaches

Attempts to decolonise and Indigenise GLAMs and the research activities they support and enable must be grounded in an acknowledgement that these institutions are neither neutral nor safe for Indigenous communities (Anderson and Christen 2019a, 2019b; Caswell, Punzalan, and Sangwand 2017; Christen 2011, 2015; Gilliland and Caswell 2016; Janke and Iacovino 2012; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; McKemmish, Faulkhead, and Russell 2011; O’Neal 2019; Thorpe 2014). This is, as demonstrated above, not only because of the violent colonial histories they evoke but also because of the structural systems in place, which further marginalise and exclude Indigenous peoples from participating in the engagement, management, and custodianship of their archives and cultural materials. Indeed, scholars and practitioners note the ways in which the technologies, intellectual property laws, archival and other collections frameworks, classification

systems, and digitisation processes that are employed by GLAMs and enacted upon Indigenous materials are still underpinned by colonial belief systems. Not only have these institutions historically positioned Indigenous voices as inferior, but they have also supported and benefitted from extractive processes, whether of land, natural resources and knowledge, thereby inflicting emotional, cultural, and epistemological violence against Indigenous communities (Anderson and Christen 2019a, 2019b; Duarte and Belarde-Lewis 2015; McCracken and Hogan-Stacey 2023; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; McKemmish et al. 2019; O'Neal 2015; Prosper et al. 2024; Thorpe 2021; Thorpe, Faulkhead, and Booker 2020; Wallace 2021). Indigenous activists argue that as a result it is necessary to employ new logics, systems, and archival frameworks, which recognise and help strengthen connection to Indigenous lands, knowledges, languages, and communities (Anderson and Christen 2019a, 2019b; Duarte and Belarde-Lewis 2015; Faulkhead, Bradley, and McKee 2019; Jones and Taylor 2024; McCracken and Hogan-Stacey 2023; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; McKemmish, Faulkhead, and Russell 2011; O'Neal 2019; O'Neal 2024a; Punzalan and March 2023; Thorpe 2022; Wallace 2021). Such methodological connections are particularly pertinent when considering interventions into AI systems design and critique.

Scholars and archivists engaging with Indigenous research are aware of how the word “research” is “probably one of the dirtiest words in the Indigenous world’s vocabulary” as “it stirs up silence, it conjures up bad memories, it raises a smile that is knowing and distrustful” (Smith 2021, 1). Thus, building new stewardship models for Indigenous archives requires an engagement with Indigenous land-based research methodologies and community-based research frameworks that are oriented towards interrelated strategies of resistance, decolonisation, self-determination, and Indigenisation (Dudgeon et al. 2020; Kovach 2021; Moreton-Robinson 2015; Smith 2021; Wilson 2008). Indigenous decolonial interventions into traditional academic research are thus grounded in Indigenous knowledges, perspectives, and worldviews and often examine the (un)productive tensions between Indigenous knowledge and Western science (Garrouette 2003; Nakata 2002; Smith 2021). The process of Indigenising the methodologies that are employed in academic research requires critically examining the history of Western research and its impacts on Indigenous peoples, relinquishing anthropocentric and empiricist Western paradigms, and challenging ongoing colonial legacies. This must entail adopting methodologies that are rooted in Indigenous knowledge systems, worldviews, oral traditions, and cultural practices and which centre physical and spiritual reciprocity and interconnectedness, as well as the importance of respecting Indigenous community protocols (Kovach 2021; Smith 2021; Wilson 2008). Stemming from the intellectual property that is at the heart of Indigenous knowledges, Indigenous research methodologies offer the transformative shifts needed to develop ethical archival frameworks and stewardship models that prioritise community, relationality, reciprocity, and care.

4.3. Indigenous relational Knowledges as decolonising and Indigenising research projects

As explained in the first section of this Literature Review, relationality, which is at the heart of different Indigenous knowledges, is a holistic, kin-centric, and reciprocal worldview of the physical and spiritual interconnectedness and coexistence between humans, other-than-humans (including animals, plants, waters, and spirits), and the land (Deloria 2003; Deloria and Wildcat 2001; Dudgeon et al. 2023; Gareau and Swain 2024; Kovach 2021; Moreton-Robinson 2004, 2016; TallBear 2019; Willson 2008). In turn, within Indigenous research methodologies, relationality presents itself as a condition and presupposition for respectful, responsible, and reciprocal community-based research (Dudgeon et al. 2020; Gareau et al. 2024; Kovach 2021; Moreton-Robinson 2015, 2017; Smith 2021; Wilson 2008). As such, a relational framework is pivotal for centring Indigenous knowledge systems in archival research in order to develop corrective archival frameworks and stewardship models that allow for Indigenous archives, whether physical or digital, to be (re)situated in practical

and methodological connections to Indigenous lands, knowledges, languages, and communities (Anderson and Christen 2019a, 2019b; Bird 2024; Booker 2021; Christen et al. 2022; Duarte and Belarde-Lewis 2015; Faulkhead et al. 2017; Jones and Taylor 2024; Littletree, Belarde-Lewis, and Duarte 2020; McKemmish 2011; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; McKemmish et al. 2019; O’Neal 2019; O’Neal 2024b, 2024b; Punzalan and March 2023; Wallace 2021). Archives on Country are the exemplification of this relational model. As Faulkhead and Thorpe explain,

There is a deep sense of obligation that Indigenous people feel towards managing archives in appropriate ways that encompasses spiritual, emotional and physical connections to records. There is a network of rights and responsibilities that exist within communities that are usually articulated in oral form (Faulkhead and Thorpe 2017, quoted in Hurley et al. 2024, 832).

4.4. Indigenous sovereignty and self-determination in GLAMs: moving beyond metaphorical decolonisation and symbolic recognition

Over the past two decades, interest in projects and initiatives framed as “decolonising” have increased across both the GLAM and higher education sectors. This has elicited criticism due to a propensity to frame decolonisation in metaphorical terms, equate it with other forms of social justice, and promote an understanding of sovereignty as a form of symbolic inclusion of Indigenous peoples within settler forms of sovereignty (Coulthard 2014; Moreton-Robinson 2007; A. Simpson 2014; Smith 2021; Tuck and Yang 2012). As such, within Indigenous politics, decolonial theories posit Indigenous perspectives on sovereignty as the repatriation of land from a material perspective (Land Back) and the recognition of Indigenous peoples’ relationality to the land as exceeding its materiality (Coulthard 2014; Goeman 2015; Moreton-Robinson 2004, 2007; Simpson 2014; Tuck and Yang 2012). In relation to GLAMs, this critique of decolonisation-as-metaphor has resulted in doubt over the ability of these institutions to engage in decolonial work that is not reduced to semantics or symbolic forms of inclusion, which do little to either address systemic power imbalances or redress the harm they have and continue to cause (Barrowcliffe et al. 2022; Christen and Anderson 2019a; Luker 2017; Thieberger et al. 2024; Thorpe 2019a, 2021, 2024a; Wallace 2021). For GLAMs, decolonisation is “a long-term process involving the bureaucratic, cultural, linguistic and psychological divesting of colonial power” (Smith 2012, 112). Indeed, those critical of the recent decolonial turn across the GLAM sector – critical due to a scepticism over the oftentimes performative nature of this discourse – stress the importance of reconfiguring the practices that are perceived as inherent or fundamental to these institutions.⁴

Indigenous and non-Indigenous scholars and practitioners committed to decolonising research methodologies and practices within collecting institutions argue that meaningful decolonial work requires proactive and transparent action. These institutions must respond to calls for divesting from colonial and state power in ways that recognise and uphold Indigenous communities’ sovereignty and self-determination across intellectual, territorial, and systemic dimensions (Anderson and Christen 2019a; Faulkhead 2017; Jones and Taylor 2024; Luker 2017; McKemmish et al. 2019; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; O’Neal 2019; Punzalan and March 2023; Thorpe, Faulkhead, and Booker 2020; Thorpe, Galassi, and Franks 2016; Wallace 2021). In this way, decolonisation in collecting institutions is not conceived as an end in or of itself. Rather, it is an ongoing and multidimensional process that intervenes within the colonial and imperial matrix of

⁴ For example, according to Lauren Booker (Garigal) a key way to challenge the non-neutrality of GLAMs and highlight their ongoing colonial legacies is to use appropriate terminology when speaking about the form and intent of these institutions. This leads to Booker’s suggestion that GLAMs being redefined as colonial/imperial collecting institutions rather than memory institutions (Booker 2021, 158 and 155-6).

GLAM to create spaces where Indigenous communities are sovereign and self-determinant in engaging with, controlling, and managing their information and data inside these institutions.

4.5. The United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, other protocols and consequent standards

The literature remarks that these prerequisites for effective decolonisation have a “global” amplitude. This is not only because of the commonality of these issues in collecting institutions that encase Indigenous information and knowledges recorded and stored in a variety of formats. Indeed, it is also because it falls under the *minimum standards* set by the United Nation Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). Indeed, UNDRIP outlines the rights of Indigenous peoples to self-determination in matters such as governance, culture, and language (United Nations 2007). Articles 11, 12, 13, and 31 are particularly relevant to information professionals as they stress Indigenous peoples’ self-determination in accessing, controlling, protecting, and managing any form of knowledges and materials held in collecting institutions (United Nations 2007). While not legally binding, the Declaration provides a starting point for how to engage with records and archives related to Indigenous communities. At its heart are principles of respect, recognition, and enactment of Indigenous communities’ stewardship over their knowledges and cultural materials (Jones and Taylor 2024; McCracken and Hogan-Stacey 2023; McKemmish, Chandler, and Faulkhead 2019; O’Neal 2015; O’Neal 2019; Thorpe and Galassi 2014; Wallace 2021). Settler colonial states such as the United States of America, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand, all with colonial histories of violent collection and extraction, were among the last countries to sign the Declaration. Information professionals and researchers must ground their practices within local Indigenous stewardship protocols and guidelines developed by or in partnership with Indigenous community members.

Examples of local Indigenous stewardship protocols include the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Library, Information and Resource Network (ATSILIRN)⁵ in Australia, the Protocols for Native American Archival Materials (PNAAM)⁶ in the United States of America, and the Aboriginal Archives Guide⁷ in Canada. Echoing or explicitly referencing UNDRIP, these protocols and guidelines establish appropriate practices for archivists, other information professionals, and collecting institutions when engaging with the Indigenous archives and cultural materials. They centre Indigenous communities’ sovereignty and self-determination in any aspect that is related to the stewardship and management of their archives such as intellectual property, description, attribution, access, and digitisation among others (Association of Canadian Archivists Public Awareness Committee 2007; ATSILIRN 2012; First Archivist Circle 2007; Garwood-Houng and Blackburn 2014; McCracken and Hogan-Stacey 2023; Punzalan and Marsh 2022; Raven 2023; Thorpe 2024). It is important to note that, from their development, these protocols and guidelines have faced and still face mixed receptions and incongruous applications because, like UNDRIP, they lack legal codification.⁸ In 2019, the International Council of Archives (ICA) published the Tandanya-Adelaide

⁵ “ATSILIRN - Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Library and Information Resource Network.” 2012. <https://atsilirn.aiatsis.gov.au/>.

⁶ First Archivist Circle. “Protocols for native American archival materials.” 2007. <https://www2.nau.edu/libnap-p/>.

⁷ Association of Canadian Archivists Public Awareness Committee. “Aboriginal Archives Guide.” 2007. [http://archivists.ca/sites/default/files/Attachments/Outreach_attachments/Aboriginal Archives English WEB.pdf](http://archivists.ca/sites/default/files/Attachments/Outreach_attachments/Aboriginal_Archives_English_WEB.pdf)

⁸ For instance, the Society of American Archivists only endorsed PNAAM in 2018, explaining in an apology that their rejection in 2008 and 2012 was “based in the language of cultural insensitivity and white supremacy” (Society of American Archivists 2018). In what is now Australia, Garwood and Blackburn (20) note that in 2008, a decade after the development of ATSILIRN protocols, few institutions included the protocols within a perspective of “endorsement” rather than “implementation” (6). In a more recent article titled “Transformative Praxis - Building Spaces for Indigenous Self-Determination in Libraries and Archives” (2019b), Kirsten Thorpe (Worimi, Port Stephens) argues that “the adoption of [ATSILIRN] protocols and guidelines in public libraries,

Declaration, a formal statement written by the ICA Expert Matters Indigenous Group that recognises the need to:

Re-imagine the meaning of archives as an engaging model of social memory; to embrace Indigenous worldviews and methods of creating, sharing and preserving valued knowledge. To decolonize our archival principles with Indigenous knowledge methods, to open the meaning of public archives to Indigenous interpretations, is to bring new dynamics of spirituality, ecology and Indigenous philosophy into the European traditions of archival memory (ICA 2019, 2).

As such, effective implementation of these protocols and guidelines is incumbent on collecting institutions and their transparency about what practical and transformative actions they can commit to undertaking in order to divest from colonial and institutional power structures. It also requires building long-term relationships of trust and reciprocity with Indigenous communities, creating effective and safe spaces for restitutions, and implementing archival frameworks that are land-based, knowledge-based, and community-based (Indigenous Archives Collective 2021; Lancaster 2024; Jones and Taylor 2024; Leditschke et al. 2024; O’Neal 2019; Punzalan and Marsh 2022; Thieberger et al. 2024; Thorpe and Galassi 2018; Thorpe, Faulkhead, and Booker 2020; Thorpe, Galassi, and Franks 2016; Wallace 2021). Unlike UNDRIP, Indigenous stewardship protocols and guidelines tackle concrete and archive-focused concerns, laying the foundation for establishing reciprocal and responsible relationships and partnerships between archivists, collecting institutions, and Indigenous communities.

archives, and cultural institutions have been ad-hoc and their development not aligned with appropriate plans for action” (2019. 5).

5. Indigenising AI for Indigenous Archives and Knowledge Management in GLAMs

Imagining Indigenous AI is one way to dream beyond the impoverished knowledge frameworks in which we are currently trapped, and to draw upon the abundant multiplicity of ways of being intelligent in the world to envision AI systems that co-create the futures we want.

Jason Edward Lewis, "Imagining Indigenous AI" (2023).

5.1. Indigenous data sovereignty

As previously discussed, despite the fact that First Nations Peoples have been generating, preserving, and sharing data for countless generations (Carroll, Kukutai, and Walter, 2021, 692), ongoing colonial endeavours in settler states have resulted in the suppression of Indigenous knowledges and data systems while collecting extensive datasets to justify colonial expansions (Smith 2021; Kukutai and Taylor 2016; Walter and Suina 2019). This exploitation is ongoing. Data collected by governments, non-Indigenous peoples, and organisations are still the primary sources that inform the creation of Indigenous policies and services (Walter and Carroll 2018). In response to this ongoing exploitation, key players from different countries have been joining *The International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group* within the Research Data Alliance. In 2019, the Global Indigenous Data Alliance was founded. The group aims to progress International Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Indigenous Data Governance to advance Indigenous control of Indigenous data (Global Indigenous Data Alliance GIDA, n.d.). Palawa scholar Maggie Walter (2018) traces the origin of the Indigenous data sovereignty movements to the work of the First Nations Information Governance Centre (FNIGC), which developed the model now known as OCAP® (Ownership, Control, Access, and Possession) in 1998 (First Nations Information Governance Centre, n.d.). Other country-specific networks have since been established, which have been moving at different paces (Carroll, Kukutai, and Walter 2021). Examples include the United States Indigenous Data Sovereignty Network (USA), the First Nations Information Governance Centre (Canada), and the Te Mana Raraunga Māori Data Sovereignty Network (Aotearoa New Zealand).

In Australia, the oldest national and Indigenous-led data sovereignty group is the Maiam nayri Wingara Collective (2018), which defines data sovereignty as “The right of Indigenous people to exercise ownership over Indigenous Data. Data ownership can be expressed through the creation, collection, access, analysis, interpretation, management, dissemination, and reuse of Indigenous Data” (1). The Collective asserts that Aboriginal Peoples in Australia have the right to:

- Exercise control of the data ecosystem including creation, development, stewardship, analysis, dissemination, and infrastructure.
- Data that are contextual and disaggregated (available and accessible at individual, community, and First Nations levels).
- Data that are relevant and empower sustainable self-determination and effective self-governance.
- Data structures that are accountable to Indigenous peoples and First Nations.
- Data that are protective of and respect our individual and collective interests.

The Maiam nayri Wingara Collective is influencing Government policies in Australia, for example recommending that a Bureau of Indigenous Data (Commonwealth of Australia 2023; Productivity Commission 2024).

5.2. FAIR and CARE for open data

The FAIR Principles (referring to Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of Data Assets)⁹ refer to a set of principles for ethical stewardship of machine-readable data. These were defined in 2016 in an article published in *Scientific Data* and have since been highly influential in developing machine-actionable datasets that provide maximum value to data producers, publishers and users (Wilkinson et al. 2016). However, various sources argue that the FAIR Principles are an incomplete tool to support Indigenous leadership over data (Carroll et al. 2021; Global Indigenous Data Alliance n.d.). The FAIR Principles, in common with other frameworks within the open data movement, primarily focus on facilitating data sharing and therefore often disregard power differentials and historical contexts. This emphasis creates tension for First Nations Peoples in need of proclaiming greater control over the application and use of Indigenous data and Indigenous Knowledge for collective benefit (Research Data Alliance International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group 2019, 1). In response, in 2018 the International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group (within the Research Data Alliance) drafted the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance as a means of filling this gap. The first formal edition of the *CARE Principles for Indigenous Data* was published in 2020 (Carroll et al. 2021). Today, the CARE Principles are promoted by the Global Indigenous Data Alliance (GIDA) (Global Indigenous Data Alliance n.d.), and are defined as Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics. The CARE Principles seek to shift data relationships from regulated consultation to value-based dialogue that foregrounds Indigenous cultures and knowledge systems within data ecosystems (Carroll, Kukutai, and Walter 2021, 697). The principles are people- and purpose-oriented and reflect the crucial role of data in advancing innovation, governance, and self-determination among Indigenous Peoples (Global Indigenous Data Alliance n.d.). The CARE Principles do not disregard the existing data-centric approach in the *FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship*. Instead, they recommend complementing them, encouraging individuals and organisations to #BeFAIRandCARE when approaching Indigenous data (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, n.d.).

5.3. Focus on frameworks

Internationally, IFLA authored a Statement on Libraries and Artificial Intelligence (2020), which explores the role of libraries in the human rights impacts of AI. The UNESCO 2021 *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*, for example, calls for a value system for AI that promotes inclusiveness, justice, equity, and interconnectedness in order to ensure that AI systems do not segregate, objectify, or undermine freedom and autonomous decision-making (UNESCO 2021). In the Australian library sector, the Australian Library Association (ALIA) including ALIA VET Libraries Australia (ALIA VLA), the Council of Australian University Librarians (CAUL), National and State Libraries Australasia (NSLA), CAVAL, AI4LAM and Open Access Australasia (OAA) published the *Joint submission from library and information related organisations to the inquiry into generative artificial intelligence in the Australian education system* (Australian Library and Information Association (ALIA) 2023). In this document there is a section related to First Nations people that states that the scraping of material from the internet contravenes the principles of respect, self-determination, cultural protocols, and community consultation emphasised in the document. Recommendations focus on Indigenous participation, staff training, respect of ICIP protocols and federal and state leadership. Indigenous protocols have also arisen over the last decade in Australia and overseas. For example, *Out of the Black Box: Indigenous protocols for AI*, created by the Indigenous Protocol and Artificial Intelligence Working Group addresses “The need for Indigenous AI to be regional in nature, conception, design and development, to be tethered to

⁹ The FAIR Principles are managed by the GO FAIR Initiative, a “bottom-up, stakeholder-driven and self-governed initiative that aims to implement the FAIR Data principles.” Further details about FAIR, and the GO FAIR Initiative can be found at the following URL: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

localised Indigenous laws inherent to Country, to be guided by local protocols to create the diverse standards and protocols required for the developmental processes of AI, and to be designed with our future cultural interrelationships and interactions with AIs in mind” (Abdilla et al. 2021).

5.4. Challenges and opportunities of AI for Indigenous peoples and Knowledges

The literature highlights that many of the challenges Indigenous peoples and communities currently face—and will continue to face with the growth of AI—relate to the exploitation and reinforcement of colonial decision-making and representation models. While many themes and challenges have emerged from this review, the following section focuses on two key issues.

The first concerns a lack of transparency and justice. As “data subjects”, Indigenous peoples are included in data aggregations that cluster interests defined by data analysts and controllers. This raises the important point that Indigenous identifiers “Need not be explicitly included in algorithms for Indigenous people to experience the disproportionate impacts of algorithm-informed decision-making” (Walter and Kukutai 2018, 4). The key questions, now explored by Indigenous Sovereignty movements, is: Who owns Indigenous data, and how should they be used? Who will be benefiting from the exploitation of data? (Walter and Kukutai 2018). The same question of exploitation and lack of benefits and attribution is raised in terms of illicit appropriation of ICIP rights in art (Janke 2024). Creating artworks with AI that misappropriate ICIP without undergoing consultation or obtaining free and prior consent can also propagate a flow of false information about Indigenous peoples and cultural practices (Janke 2024). This warning is an example of the scenarios that can happen in library settings when communities have never validated datasets used by AI. Transparency is also needed in areas like pollution and land management. AI research and development is currently mirroring extractive, exploitative, and environmentally excessive patterns seen in mass technologies since the Industrial Revolution which can lead to a continued exploitation of Indigenous lands and resources (Abdilla 2018; Lewis 2023). Indeed, all technologies, particularly AI, play a dual role: they contribute to solutions for mitigating the climate crisis, yet they also drive pollution through the extraction of natural resources for their production, significant energy consumption required for their operation, electronic waste disposal. However, public awareness about AI's impact on climate change and its influence on land ownership is lacking (Dhar 2020). A growing disparity remains in how different regions and communities experience the environmental impacts of AI, replicating differences between global north and south (Kanungo 2023; Ren and Wierman 2024).

Secondly, AI can exacerbate existing bias and stereotypes and consequently increase existing inequalities (Walter and Kukutai 2018). This happens especially when non-Indigenous people use AI to inform themselves about Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and cultures without remembering that the information provided could be incorrect or history could be told by a univocal lens (Fitch et al. 2023). The big data used by AI are mostly not controlled or checked by Indigenous peoples. One of the key things that developers can do to mitigate bias in AI is hiring more intentionally and collaborating with the communities impacted by their technologies (Tapu and Fa’agau 2022). Moreover, with the increased calls to digitise Indigenous knowledges, growing concerns are expressed regarding the protection and the preservation of these knowledges within the custodianship of Indigenous communities (Nakata 2007). Indeed, the homogeneous nature of existing structures of digitisation are inadequate in capturing the complexity and the diversity of Indigenous knowledge systems (Nakata 2007). As such, it is likely that AI systems in their current states may exacerbate the homogenization of Indigenous knowledge systems, leading to their fragmentation and loss.

5.5. Learning from and getting inspired by Indigenous use of AI technologies

Heather Igloliorte, Julie Nagam, and Carla Taunton (2016, 11) assert that ‘technology’ has always been a tool of Indigenous resilience and cultural continuity as well as a conduit for storytelling. For

millennia, Aboriginal peoples have developed myriad scientific processes and technologies based on the relational knowledges and cultural practices of “Aboriginal social cohesion, well-being, environmental sustainability, culture and spirituality” (Abdilla 2018, 67). Despite these challenges, an increasing number of Indigenous communities worldwide are working to preserve and share this cultural heritage, and AI can play a valuable role in supporting these efforts. Indeed, there is a growing interest in bringing Indigenous interventions to AI systems. This was amply reflected in the 2019 Indigenous Protocol and AI Workshops where a group of Indigenous artists, scholars, and knowledge keepers across from Aotearoa, Australia, North America, and the Pacific gathered in Honolulu, Hawai’i to re-think AI and its futures from Indigenous standpoints (Lewis 2023). These conversations were grounded in Indigenous protocols that refer to the ways in which diverse Indigenous communities conceive relationships between human and other-than-humans (Abdilla 2018). These workshops culminated in a position paper that articulates “suggestions about how to rethink the design of AI systems from a perspective that takes into account ethical frameworks resonant across many Indigenous cultures” (Lewis 2020). The paper’s authors identify seven starting points and guidelines “for Indigenous-centered AI Design” (Lewis 2020):

- Designing AI systems in partnership with local communities
- Grounding the foundation of AI systems within relationality and reciprocity
- Responsibility and accountability to Indigenous communities
- Applying Indigenous protocols in AI governance and regulation guidelines
- Recognising the cultural and social nature of technologies
- Applying ethical design to the full stack of a technology
- Respecting and supporting Indigenous data sovereignty

Some other examples in the Australian context include Mikaela Jade, founder and CEO of tech company Indigital, a pioneer in using AI technologies to include Elders stories in national parks, sharing culture with tourists visiting important sites for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples (Hislop 2021). In collaboration with CSIRO, in the wetlands of Kakadu National Park, rangers are using AI and Indigenous knowledge to adaptively track and manage this country (Cranney 2019). In Stradbroke Island, the Quandamooka Yoolooburrabee Aboriginal Corporation are combining drones and AI with ancient knowledge to save a unique population of koalas from the wildfires that could wipe them out (WWF 2024). The rural town of Laura, about 330 kilometres from Cairns, which is surrounded by over 10,000 rock art sites and is successfully utilising AI in apps to tag them and store them in a database to allow discoverability for rangers and schools (Richards 2023).

Furthermore, several Indigenous startups and organisations across the world are responding to these opportunities by building their own AI tools to support different aims. For example, wâsikan kisewâtisiwin, an Indigenous-led startup based in Amiskwaciwâskahikan/Edmonton in Canada, is currently developing AI tools to assist in identifying anti-Indigenous bias. wâsikan kisewâtisiwin, which means “kind electricity” in Cree, is working with the Alberta Machine Intelligence Institute (Amii) to develop two AI tools, one of which monitors anti-Indigenous bias and hate speech on social media, and the other being a plug-in that will help correct bias and racism against Indigenous Peoples in writing (Appel 2024). Other instances include speech recognition used for language resources, augmented and mixed realities to tell stories, land management, and many others (Walter and Kukutai 2018). A large project worthy of mention is *Abundant Intelligences*. Despite not being oriented to the library sector, *Abundant Intelligences*, led by Jason Edward Lewis, is interesting as an Indigenous-led, Indigenous-majority international, interdisciplinary research program that imagines new ways of conceptualising and designing AI software based on Indigenous knowledge systems. Their approach is grounded in the Indigenous epistemologies containing robust conceptual frameworks for understanding how technology can be developed in ways that integrate it into existing lifeways, support the flourishing of future generations, and are optimised for abundance rather than scarcity. The project goal is to advance methods for improving AI to better serve

everybody through exploring and developing culturally grounded AI systems that support Indigenous ways of knowing. Their path toward this is to build culturally grounded AI systems that support Indigenous sovereignty and ways of knowing (Tapu and Fa'agau 2022.)

In summary, although regulations exist and the library sector in Australia is actively engaging with AI, there is a gap in the literature regarding critical analysis of AI applications in libraries that incorporate Indigenous knowledge. While each country and community may have unique characteristics, concerns around data ownership, participation, benefit-sharing, and transparency show similarities on a global scale. Several Indigenous projects utilising various AI technologies, grounded in Indigenous principles, worldviews, objectives, and governance, offer promising examples of what can be achieved when Western systems are de-centred to allow space for alternative “intelligences.”

Libraries are likely to benefit from such initiatives, which showcase the potential for AI systems to be designed by, and for, Indigenous peoples and in line with Indigenous protocols. However, this review has demonstrated that the collections upon which any library-developed tool is based are inevitably collections from organisations that represent acts of colonial power, extraction, and violence. Therefore, in addition to considering how the process of AI development can be Indigenised, libraries and researchers will need to develop techniques for understanding the legacies of colonial history within the library and archival datasets that will underpin AI work in the sector. Scholars in the Digital Humanities have attempted to explain how the representational forces of humanities data shape our understanding. Johanna Drucker (2011) argues, for instance, that *data* needs to be rethought of as *capta*: something that is taken and constructed rather than representative of objective truth. Drucker argues for a fundamental point that holds itself relevant in this context: “the more profound challenge we face is to accept the ambiguity of knowledge, the fundamentally interpreted condition on which data is constructed” (Drucker 2011). This suggests a need not just to reimagine AI development, but to reflect upon the collections, and associated practices, embedded within the library sector.

6. Recommendations

This Literature Review has shown that the respectful management of Indigenous Knowledges in AI is a complex and multifaceted matter. As many of the authors discussed above argue, more work is necessary to fully comprehend the potential and the dangers that AI present for the library sector. New approaches are therefore needed to tackle the challenges that are ahead of the information sector, in Australia and overseas. Despite protocols and laws arising in this area, there remains a gap regarding frameworks for practical application and governance structures. Despite focusing primarily on libraries, the recommendations presented below could also benefit other types of GLAM institution. Indigenous authors teach us that knowledge exists everywhere and takes many forms, which highlights the importance of approaching this work as both transdisciplinary and transnational. The following propositions highlight the significant gap in the literature and provide a roadmap for future studies. Based on the reviewed papers in this Literature Review, we identified the following areas of improvement:

- **Identifying and understanding the White possessive logic that shapes AI** principles and applications in libraries is the first step towards revealing the inequalities it perpetuates.
- **Embracing Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Governance** principles and frameworks as key to thinking critically about matters such as ICIP rights, control and benefit sharing.
- **Centring Indigenous knowledge systems** and implementing Indigenous relational protocols. Rethinking AI systems and algorithms within Indigenous relational protocols that centres social and environmental sustainability through kinship and ethics of stewardship.
- **Making community-based and participatory approaches** a priority. Communities, when collaborating with others, should be involved in the design of the technology itself. Collaborative engagements with Indigenous peoples based on care responsibility and reciprocity should be grounded in projects that involve AI and Indigenous knowledges.
- **Investing in training and knowledge translation practices** that ensure Indigenous ways of seeing AI work in libraries are non-negotiable. This will strengthen collaboration, encourage transdisciplinary exchange, and enrich the collective process of meaning-making in the use of AI technologies.
- **Understanding the conditions in which machine-actionable data have been created.** Institutions and individuals should understand, and transparently record, the situatedness of data arising from library collections. This will enhance accountability and support responsible AI practices in the sector.

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